

Article

Student Radicalism and Democracy in Post_Left Bengal

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Abstract

Since May 2011, West Bengal has seen a major political change.. The ruling Left Front was routed in the elections and a new political combine of the Congress-Trinamul captured political power. Since May 2011, elections have been held in panchayats, municipalities, students unions, etc. The objective of the present paper is to examine (1) whether students union elections have been truly democratic; (2) whether the present generation of students is in favour of radical social change. These research queries are being answered on the basis of content analysis of news reports and empirical studies done as part of an ongoing UGC's Major Research Project entitled Student Radicalism in Post-Left Bengal.

Key words: democracy, student union, radicalism, referendum, violence

Introduction

The student movement in Bengal is nearly two hundred years old. From the days of Young Bengal, the students in Bengal have played an important role in bringing about social change. They played a major role in the freedom struggle and in the mass struggles in Independent India (Banerjee A. , 1998). The study of student power movements originated in the sixties of the twentieth century. (Banerjee A. , 2003). Since then many studies have been

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done on students' politics. In the twenty-first century, we find major research projects and research papers based on projects (Banerjee, 2009), (Banerjee A. , 2012) , independent research papers (Sarkar A. , 2012) and popular articles (Bandyopadhyay, 2014). That apart, student movements are widely reported in the media and columnists analyze them.

The present paper is based on early findings of an ongoing UGC Major Research Project entitled "Student Radicalism in Post-Left Bengal"¹. The objective of this study is to study the relation between student radicalism and democracy. We will firstly examine 1)to what extent student union elections have been truly democratic;2) whether the present generation of students are in favour of radical social change. I have used the term 'radicalism 'in the sense I used it previously, i.e., as an advocacy for drastic social change along socialistic lines. (Banerjee A. , 2003, p. 72).I would use the term 'democracy ' in the sense that the ancient Greeks used it as 'rule by the people'. As Rittberger rightly observes, the term 'democracy' is also synonymous with majority rule.² In 450 BC the great democratic leader of Athens, Pericles, argued that democracy is lined with toleration³.

Methodology of the Study

The present study is based on news analysis and survey work. For news analysis of students union elections, we used news reports of one Bengali newspaper, the Ananda Bazaar Patrika .The period covered was 14th January to 3rd March 2014. For survey work we covered four universities; namely, Burdwan University, Calcutta University, Presidency University and Jadavpur University. The a pilot survey is a small scale test of a research instrument , run in advance of the main fieldwork and used to test the utility of a research design. (Scott, 2009) It was felt by the Principal Investigator that the students studying social sciences may be better informed about current social issues .Hence

they could properly advise him with regard to what to include in and what to exclude from the main questionnaire. Hence students from social science disciplines were covered in the pilot survey. Accidental sampling was used. The idea was to get insights about student radicalism.

Indian Democracy in Crisis

India is the largest democracy of the world. But the million dollar question is: how healthy is our democracy? Noted political commentator, Amal Kumar Mukhopadhyay, observes that Indian democracy declined in the 1990s. He approvingly quotes Kaviraj, who claimed that Indian democracy has moved more heavily towards a right of centre ideological vortex far removed from the ideals of Nehru and Gandhi. According to Mukhopadhyay Indian democracy has been hamstrung 'by the Siamese twins of globalization and communalization (Mukhopadhyay, 2005, p. 8). In the second decade of the twenty-first century, Mukhopadhyay's words still ring true. We now have the Bharatiya Janata Party in power at the centre. It is the same party, under the same leader, Narendra Modi which has been accused of orchestrating the communal holocaust in Gujarat. In 2002.4 under Narendra Modi, the BJP captured state power on the 'development' plank, with promises of 'acche din'. And it is embarking on an ambitious process of liberalization which would effectively privatize all state assets which are owned by the people, and curtail the freedom of the working class, while making India a happy hunting ground for exploitation by the Indian and foreign bourgeoisie⁵.

Our main concern is with studying student radicalism and democracy in contemporary West Bengal. But do we really behave democratically? Can our students have any respect for parliamentary democracy, when the elected representatives of the ruling party

behave in an undemocratic and uncouth manner? Let us look at the experience of some school children. They had gone to visit the West Bengal State Assembly on 13th February 2014. It was part of an educational tour. Criticism of government policies is a major function of the Opposition. At that time Manas Bhuiya, who is a Congress MLA reportedly attacked the many failings of the ruling party. In retaliation, the Chief Whip of Trinamul Congress, Sobhandeb Chattopadhyay, reportedly used unparliamentary language against the MLA. For the eighty six students studying in Class X in Holy Child School, taken to the Assembly by their teachers for a firsthand experience of how democracy works, it was a rude culture shock. Sobhandeb Chattopadhyay's uncharitable comments on Manas Bhuiya prompted the students to walk out. Some of the students, Payel Sarkar, Sanjana Mukhopadhyay, Gairika Sahara, etc., said that they were deeply disappointed at the lack of discipline in the Assembly. They said that it is not possible to remain here for a long time. Another student was far more critical. She said that her experience proves the truth of Lenin's view that Parliament is nothing but a pig sty⁶.

Students Union Elections 2014 in West Bengal

Since May 2011, we find that the student movement has changed direction. Previously, under the left Front rule, the majority of college unions were dominated by students organizations subscribing to a leftist ideology. On 13th May, 2011, the Trinamul-Congress combine ousted the ruling Left Front government. This event was hailed by the people as Paribartan. Political scientists have analyzed the election results and delineated the causes of the defeat of the Left Front (Chakrabarty, 2011), (Datta Gupta, 2011). After paribartan, we find that politics in West Bengal

has taken a right-wing turn. And this has been reflected in the students movement also. The student arm of the ruling party, the Trinamul Chattra Parishad, has been accused of letting loose a reign of terror in colleges and universities. College after college is becoming a battleground, not between competing ideologies, but between warring groups of students for the loaves and fishes of office. In college after college it has been alleged that the student wing of the ruling party, the Trinamul Chattra Parishad(TMCP) was taking recourse to foul means to prevent student organizations of opposition parties from contesting elections. In Dr. Sahidullah Smriti Mahavidyalaya, violence occurred between TMCP and Chattra Parishad(CP)⁷. In a single day (13th January) we find campus violence occurred in widely dispersed colleges. Thus, Kalipada Ghosh Tarai Mahavidyalaya(Bagdogra) Manindra Chandra College(Kolkata), Surya Sen Mahavidyalaya(Siliguri) and Krishnanath College, Baharampur⁸. Obviously, there is a method in this madness. In the majority of cases, student activists owing allegiance to TMCP used violence. They used tactics of intimidation to foil the attempts of opposition groups to file nominations. They would stop at nothing, including murder of political opponents, to ensure their victory in students union elections. In some cases, opposition student groups resisted these attempts of TMCP activists by force. As a result there were clashes. In many places the leftists put up a stiff resistance. Thus, in Chaipath college, Daspur, West Medinipur, there was conflict between SFI & TMCP leaving 10 injured⁹. Faced with such violence, the leaders of the Students Federation of India(SFI) wisely decided to withdraw from student union elections in Bankura colleges.¹⁰ Of the thirty colleges under Burdwan University, the SFI could file nominations in only Katwa College and Ranigunj Girls College¹¹. But eliminating opposition groups did not always ensure a smooth cakewalk for the TMCP for they had to contend with infighting among themselves. Thus

at Durgapur Michael Madhusudan Memorial College¹², and Tarakeswar Degree College¹³, we find infighting among student activists of TMCP.

These student activists, whose activities would have been labelled 'criminal' in any other society, were given a clean chit by the Chief Minister of West Bengal, and Trinamul supremo, Ms. Mamata Banerjee, who claimed in a speech that naughtiness (dushtumi) is the hallmark of youth. Can gun battles between college students, as happened at Kaliachak College,¹⁵ qualify as naughtiness? Can political murder by college students qualify as naughtiness? Only the Chief Minister can answer.

The net result of this unprecedented violence was that the TMCP won the student union elections. But was it a real victory? The TMCP claimed to have won the majority of seats in Calcutta University, a claim hotly contested by the SFI. According to the SFI Secretary, Debyajyoti Das, the TMCP contested over 800 seats but could not win more than 50% but the SFI contested only 173 seats and won 129. Due to opposition from TMCP¹⁶ Even the darkest cloud has a silver lining, says an English proverb. Amidst all this organized mayhem, the decision of the authorities of Presidency University, to make elections as transparent as possible by going for online filing of nominations, marks a refreshing change in the prevailing political culture of violence and hooliganism.¹⁷

From the above analysis we may conclude that the student union elections under the present regime had made a farce of democracy. When opposition student groups are not allowed to file nominations, when the Trinamul Chattra Parishad, with the blessings of their Supremo, Mamata Banerjee, uses violence and muscle power to capture student unions, can we call the elections democratic? As Subhas Sarkar (Sarkar S., 2007) rightly pointed out, "Though the aims and objectives of the student union of

different universities and institutes of higher learning are generally maintained, in recent times, the intrusion of political influence of different parties is trying to derail the very objectives and processes". His words have great relevance for contemporary Bengal where every student union is seen by the ruling party as not an instrument to politically socialize the young but as a power centre to be captured by hook or by crook.

Student Radicalism & Democracy

From the Pilot Study on student radicalism, referred to previously, we find that of the 72 students studied, 27(37% of the present sample) are radical, 15(21%) are liberal and 23(32%) are conservative. 7(10%) are neutral. Thus we find that a minority of the students are radical. But if we combine the radical and the liberal we find that 58% of the sample is either radical or liberal. Thus we find that in spite of paribartan, a substantial section of the student community adheres to left-wing ideology¹⁸. (Banerjee A. , 2014)This had implications for the student movement. In Presidency University, where radicals predominate, the TMCP did not even try to file nominations.¹⁹The student organization was already handicapped by rampage indulged by the TMCP inside the university premises, a year ago. At Jadavpur University, the SFI won elections to the Arts student union.²⁰

Two Referendums

Presidency University

Student radicals have shown that, left to themselves, they can successfully organize democratic processes. I will give two examples. The first one is from Presidency University. Presidency has had a long tradition of radicalism beginning from the days of Young Bengal. (Sarkar S. , 1995).The institute was a hotbed of student radicalism in the heydays of Naxalite movement in the sixties and seventies.

(Raychaudhuri, 1987)And the students have retained their leftist commitment even after the institution was promoted to university status. Since the Trinamul Congress came to power, it has devised the system of mentor groups for all universities. The mentor group nominates a panel of individuals for the post of Vice Chancellor and advises the university in administrative matters. Sugata Bose is the chairman of the 10 member mentor group of Presidency University. In the last Parliamentary elections, held in 2014, he was nominated by the Trinamul Congress as a Trinamul candidate to contest the Parliamentary elections. But the students did not take kindly to this decision. A year ago, in 2013, Trinamul activists had ransacked Presidency University. So, quite naturally, the students were angry with Sugata Bose for accepting the nomination. They saw this as betrayal of their institution and their cause. Their protest took the form of a referendum, which they claim was unprecedented in India, though precedents are found in institutions abroad. "This was just a polite way of letting him (Sugata Bose) know that students want him to resign," said Neelabjo Banerjee, a third-year student of history at Presidency University.²¹

Romita Datta reported on Mar 29 2014:

When wooden letter boxes were emptied on Friday to count the votes, it was found that 1,208 students, or about 78.7% of those who voted, wanted Bose to resign. Of the university's 2,135 students, 1,534 (71.8%) cast their votes on Wednesday and Thursday—only 151 short of those who voted in last month's students' union election²².

While the outcome of the referendum showed that the students wanted Bose to resign, he has, till now, not honoured its verdict.

Jadavpur University

My second example is from Jadavpur University. Like Presidency University, Jadavpur University has also a long tradition of leftism. Unlike Presidency, which was set up by the colonial administration, The National Council of Education, out of which Jadavpur University was later born, was the outcome of the Swadeshi Movement. It was the first National College and was headed by the revolutionary Aurobindo Ghosh.

The recent student activism at Jadavpur University started in September 3, 2014. The students were agitated over the assault of a female student in the campus by some males. The authorities were insensitive to the incident which once more indicated that women are not safe anywhere in West Bengal. To quell the protests, the acting Vice Chancellor, Abhijit Chakrabarty, ordered police action on the unarmed students. The police responded with alacrity. It was alleged by the students that the police brutally assaulted the male students and molested the female students at the instance of the Vice Chancellor. Television footage and pictures of the police action which were flashed in the newspapers provided substance to their allegations²³. This started the #Hok kolorob movement which spread to one hundred cities throughout the world. The students demanded the resignation of the Vice Chancellor. But the government was in no mood to accept the demands of the students. Earlier, the government had tweaked the rules for appointing Vice Chancellors to ensure that the will of the government will prevail in every case. The bill made it mandatory for the Chancellor to consult the Education Minister before appointing a Vice Chancellor²⁴. Since the government sided with Abhijit Chakrabarty, the Chancellor had no alternative than to appoint

him as the permanent Vice Chancellor. This infuriated the student community and the teachers²⁵.

It is under these circumstances that the students decided to hold a referendum on the resignation of the Vice Chancellor. The first referendum was held on 30th and 31st October, 2014. The outcome of the referendum revealed that 97% of the Arts Faculty students wanted Vice Chancellor, Abhijit Chakrabarty to resign. Though the referendum had no legal validity, its social and political significance was great. One of the observers, Sujato Bhadra said that its results have social acceptance. Another observer, Ruby Mukhopadhyay, had even opined that the results of the referendum could be of use to anyone who wanted to take any legal step in the Jadavpur University issue.²⁶ The Governor of West Bengal and Chancellor of Jadavpur University, Sri Kesharinath Tripathi questioned the validity of the referendum²⁷. Being a political man, he should realize that rebellions are never legal. In the second referendum, held on 12th November, 2014, 97% of the engineering students of Jadavpur University wanted him to resign²⁸. Thus the results of both the referendums thus went against the Vice Chancellor. From these referendums it is evident that the Vice Chancellor has lost his moral standing in the eyes of the students. But, like Sugata Bose, Abhijit Chakrabarty has, till now, not honoured the verdict of the referendum. So, the stalemate in Jadavpur University continues, with both teachers and students boycotting the Vice Chancellor.

From these anecdotes it is clear that though the students introduced direct democratic methods to determine the credibility of the officials in power, they have not honoured the verdict of the students. It is clear that these two dignitaries who were appointed by the Government do not care for democratic norms. In the process, Prof. Sugata Bose and

Prof. Abhijit Chakraborty have set a very bad example to the student community. They have emerged as power loving people who do not care for the students whom they are supposed to serve.

Discussion

Democracy, as we know it involves rule by the majority. It also means tolerance of others who do not see eye to eye with the majority, free and fair polls in which all contestants have equal chance of being elected..But the student union elections under the Trinamul regime have not been democratic. Though the Trinamul Congress leaders swear by democracy, their conduct throughout the period of their rule have not been congruent with democratic norms. Be it the panchayat, municipal or Parliamentary elections, there have been systematic attempts to browbeat political opponents through organized hooliganism and terrorization of opponents. A possible explanation is that that the ruling party sees the college unions as power centres which must be captured by hook or by crook. The Chief Minister has, in fact, condoned such violence by youths belonging to her party by lightly dismissing these incidents as incidence of naughtiness((dustumi), whereas she is quick to condemn violence by other political parties. Yet, it has been repeatedly pointed out by those educationists associated with higher education that the function of the student union is to politically socialize the students. (Sarkar S., 2007; Sinha, 1419, B.S.). In West Bengal goal displacement has occurred. Instead of being viewed as an agent of political socialization, student unions are viewed as power centres. Hence the organized violence unleashed primarily by the cadres of the student wing of the ruling party, namely, Trinamul Chattra Parishad.

The political situation in West Bengal in 2014 resembles that seen in Italy during the

regime of Mussolini in the 1920s. In a poem, Sankhya Ghosh paraphrased through rhyme what Romain Rolland and his friends had told Rabindranath Tagore, who had gone to visit Italy in 1926:

"In a country without a rule of law,

where only the will of the dictator is law,

In every locality butchers make merry with the flesh of innocents."²⁹

The present day rulers of Bengal do not make any pretence of following democratic norms after capturing power. Like the Fascist Party, the Trinamul Congress is organized on the basis of monism, fundamentalism and conspiracy theories³⁰. The party begins and ends with Mamata Banerjee (Didi) whose style of functioning is very similar to dictators. From what we see and read in the media, we find that Didi's word is law, whether in the party or in the government. Other leaders are her obedient followers at best, or her servants at the worst. Whenever Didi is in trouble, and she is in a lot of trouble nowadays, owing to the involvement of her party leaders in the Saradha scam, she smells conspiracy from the BJP or other parties.³¹ Like all dictators, Didi relies on only blind belief from the masses - no questions asked. ³². When she was asked an 'uncomfortable' question by a college student, in a televised programme on IBN Live (19 May, 2012), Didi promptly labelled her a Maoist and walked out of the show.³³ Critics of ruling party claim that the Trinamul Congress is not averse to hobnobbing with the communal and fundamentalist and anti-national elements has been shown by their connection with Khagragarh blasts³⁴.

In the present political situation youth are fast losing their respect for politicians of all hues. From childhood, our students are seeing how democratic norms are being thrown to the

four winds by our political leaders. It was reported in the Press that their 'unparliamentary behaviour' in the Assembly (Bidhan Sabha) has antagonized school children who have compared the legislature to a pig sty. Political violence in colleges is antagonizing the ordinary students who come here to study and build careers. Sarkar found that "there is widespread opinion that college politics is heightening destructive activities". (Sarkar A. , 2012, p. 94)

Here are some of his salient findings.

- 1) The majority of the students(60%) opine that the teaching-learning process is hampered by college politics.
- 2) A majority(87.5%) of the students believe that college union leads to various problems which impede the smooth functioning of the college.
- 3)34% of the students say that unrest and agitation are the outcome of college union elections.
- 4)An absolute majority of the students(91%) do not support violence.
- 5) The majority of the students(65%) hold that college politics creates rift among students.
- 6)72.5% of the students are of the opinion that student politics should be free of mainstream politics
- 7) A key finding of the study is that political participation of the students is steadily declining.

These findings of Sarkar need to be carefully studied by our educational administrators and correctional measures should be initiated to make student politics a real instrument of political socialization .

Some of our university students have , however, shown remarkable political maturity. The students of Presidency University and Jadavpur University have used an instrument of direct democracy, namely the referendum , to send political messages to the authorities which they may disregard with peril. Their pioneering examples may be emulated in other institutes. These political actions show that despite the onslaught of fascist forces on the student movement, the student movement has not lost its democratic moorings.

Concluding Remarks

The 40th All India Sociological Conference has been organized on the theme "Development, Diversity & Democracy". I have chosen to speak on one aspect of the theme namely Democracy and its relation to Student Radicalism. However development, diversity and democracy are interlinked. Democracy itself is linked to tolerance of diversity. And democracy from the bottom up is the sine qua non for proper development of all sections of our people. We have seen that in West Bengal, development of youth is being impeded by the prevalent political culture of violence, and anarchy which is raging throughout the state. Bengali teenagers and youth are today totally disillusioned with the political and educational system. And this disillusionment manifests itself in the numerous student agitations. Despite all these handicaps , a few elite student groups have shown that they can effectively employ instruments of direct democracy, like referendum, as means of protest.

We have seen that student union elections in West Bengal have been marked by violence and mayhem. Can the same observation be made in case of any other state like Uttar Pradesh or Kerala? How have other states enhanced democratic political participation by students? How can the syllabi in the school and higher levels be used to inculcate respect for

democratic norms and values among our youth? These are some of the suggestions which I place before future researchers .

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Notes

¹ See F.No.5-449/2013(HRP) dated 25 March,2014.

² Rittberger:'Democracy' in Ian Mclean & Alistair Macmillan:Oxford concise Dictionary of Politics,Oxford University Press, Oxford, New york, etc.,Second Edition, 2003,p.139.

³ Ibid.

⁴ See Basudeb Chattopadhyay, Ashis Ranjan Guha,and Ramkrishna Chatterjee(compiled and edited)Communalism Condemned:Gujarat Genocide 2002,Netaji Insititute for Asian Studies,and West Bengal College & University Teachers Association,Kolkata, 2002.

⁵ For latest developments see for example, relevant issues of *Frontline*,October 3,2014(Cover story on BJP-"What is the BJP upto?"),October 31,2014(Cover story:"Mega Sale"- on selling Public Sector Undertakings),November 14,2014(Cover story:"Labour under Attack), etc.

⁶ Nijassha Sangbaddata:"Bidhayakder bisrinkhalae gallery charlo chattrira" , report in *Ananda Bazar Patrika*, Kolkata,14 February,2014,p.8.

⁷ Vide *Ananda Bazar Patrika* 22 January 2014

⁸ Vide *Ananda Bazar Patrika* 14 January 2014

⁹ Vide *Ananda Bazar Patrika* 18 January 2014

¹⁰ Vide *Ananda Bazar Patrika* 21 January 2014

¹¹ Vide *Ananda Bazar Patrika* 22 January 2014

¹² Vide *Ananda Bazar Patrika* 23 January 2014

¹³ Vide *Ananda Bazar Patrika* 19 January 2014

¹⁴ Vide *Ananda Bazar Patrika* 31 January 2014

¹⁵ Vide *Ananda Bazar Patrika* 29 January 2014

¹⁶ Vide *Ananda Bazar Patrika*, 19 January, 2014.

¹⁷ Nijassha Sangbaddata: "Online vote debar pathe egocche Presidency", report in *Ananda Bazar Patrika*, Kolkata, 15 January, 2014, p.7.

¹⁸ I had extensively reported my findings at a seminar lecture at the Indian Statistical Institute, Kolkata on 6th June, 2014.

¹⁹ "Presidency nirbachane anupasthit TMCP", *Ananda Bazar Patrika*, 12 January, 2014, p.8.

²⁰ Vide *Ananda Bazar Patrika* 30 January 2014

²¹ Cited in Romita Datta "Students hold referendum to oust professor fighting LS poll" <http://www.livemint.com/Politics/hBIUUn2MlzwORKoQpoinSK/Referendum-to-oust-professor-fighting-LS-poll-as-Trinamool.html>. downloaded on 25.11.2014. (Emphasis mine)

²² Datta, loc.cit.

²³ See Nijassha Sangbaddata: "Andhakare abadh mar"-report in *Ananda Bazar Patrika*, Kolkata, 18th September, 2014.

²⁴ See Nijassha Sangbaddata: "Fer ain badal, Upacharya niyoge niyantran baralo rajya",-report in *Ananda Bazar Patrika*, Kolkata, 11 July, 2014, p.7.

²⁵ By a Staff Reporter "Protest cloud on VC appointment", *The Telegraph*, 8th October, 2014, p.10.

²⁶ Cited in Nijassha Sangbaddata: "Abhijiter istafar pakkhei rai ganabhoter " ",-report in *Ananda Bazar Patrika*, Kolkata, 1st November, 2014, p.6.

²⁷ TNN "Governor questions Jadavpur University students' referendum", TNN, November 3, 2014 <http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/kolkata/Governor-questions-jadavpur-University-students-referendum/articleshow/45016334.cms>. downloaded on 11.11.2014.

²⁸ Nijassha Sangbaddata: " Abhijiterpashe nei engineering poruarao" report in *Ananda Bazar Patrika*, Kolkata, 13th November, 2014, p.1&6.

²⁹ Sankhya Ghosh "Italite Kabi "in *Saradiya Desh* 1421, p.141. (Translated by me)

³⁰ Stan Taylor: "Fascism" in Ian McLean & Alistair Mcmillan ed. *Oxford Concise Dictionary of Politics*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, New York, etc. Second Edition, 2003, p.193.

³¹ On recent critiques of Mamata Banerjee's style of functioning see the cover story in *Saptahik Bartaman*, 18th October, 2014. In this issue, three writers-Rantideb Sengupta, Subhashis Maitra and Jayanto Sengupta analysed what is wrong with Mamata Banerjee.

³² Kumar Rana analysed this phenomenon in contemporary India in a short article. See Kumar Rana "Prasnahinatar rajniti" in *Saradiya Hatebazare Patrika*, 1421, pp.99-100.

³³ See "Watch Mamata's stormy interaction with students" (19 May 2012). This video clip may be available on *You Tube*

³⁴ On the Khagragarh blasts and recent incidents, see recent news reports from 1st October onwards, 1st November, 2014. Here four writers -Mohit Ray, Dr.Swarup Prasad Ghosh, Dr.Bhaskar Purakayastha, and Debanjan Das have analysed the danger the country faces from Islamic militants and what we can do to remedy the situation. .